

Effect of whey Protein Consumption on the Selected Physical Fitness variables of Male Sprinters

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of whey Protein consumption on the selected physical fitness variables of male sprinters. The total number of 20 male sprinters which equally divided 10 in each group i.e. experimental and control groups. The sample was belong to, who had participated at inter college level under Lakshmbai National Institute of physical education, North east regional center in the age group of 18 to 25 years. whey Protein gives to 10 experimental groups for 12 week thrice a week of alternate days with milk. After the 12 weeks physical fitness test was taken on 20 male sprinters, experimental as well as control groups. In conclusion; keeping the results and discussion in view the conclusions drawn that the significant effect of whey Protein consumption on sprinters related to their standing broad jump (Meters), 50 yard dash (Seconds), pull-ups (Minutes), sit-ups (Minutes), shuttle run (Second), 12-min. run/walk.

Keywords:

Whey Protein, Physical fitness, Sprinters

1. INTRODUCTION

Whey protein is traditionally used for general strengthening and recovery. Every sprinter understands, or should understand, the important of protein supplementation. Sprinters required more protein than sedentary folks. Without protein (which the body breaks down into amino acids), you cannot build muscle. As far as study concerned, no matter what kind of diet one follow – whether it is low or high in complex carbohydrates or fats – and despite the number of calories you taken in, your diet must be rich with protein. There are many different types of protein sources available to all. Qualitative protein can be found in whole foods like eggs, milk, cottage cheese, beef, fish, poultry, etc. and, there are also a variety of protein supplements on the marked milk and egg protein, soy, beef, even vegetable protein. Out of all these different protein supplements, everyone absolutely convinced that whey protein is the best. Not only does it have a superior biological value (which means it may “yield” most usable grams of amino acids than other protein (supplements), it is also very low in lactose. Whey protein – ion-exchanged, micro filtered whey protein/ is extremely high quality and very easy to use which is another thing that is terrific about it. There are so many ergogenic aids for improving the performance; supplementary foods are one of them. During the training schedule or period a sportsman wants much more energy for completion of their schedule. The sources of energy in our body is limited i.e. the sportsman needs extra energy. The ultimate aim of sportsman is achieving highest performance in sports and games. If the sports are depend on strength, endurance, speed then the supplementary food is much more needed.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. STUDY DESIGN AND SETTING

Simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample. The total number of 20 male sprinters which equally divided 10 in each group i.e. experimental and control groups. The sample was belong to, who had participated at inter college level under Lakshmibai National Institute of physical education, North east regional center in the age group of 18 to 25 years.

2.2. SAMPLING TOOLS

The following physical fitness test items was used for data collection for this study was Standing broad jump (Meters), 50 yard dash (Seconds)(6), Pull-ups (Minutes), Sit -ups (Minutes), Shuttle run (4*10 yard) (Second)(5), 12 min. run/ walk (Minutes) (1).

Researcher was took the sample of 20 male sprinters. Pre-test on 10 male sprinters then divided into two groups 10 experimental and 10 control groups. After the pre-test body weight was taken of experimental group, that fall in between 50 to 59kg weight category they were taken whey Protein 2.5gm and those lie above 60kg weight category they were taken whey Protein 3gm. whey Protein give to 10 experimental groups for 12 week thrice a week of alternate days with milk. After the 12 weeks physical fitness test was taken on 20 male sprinters, experimental as well as control groups.

2.3. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

To analysis the data statistically found the significant difference between experimental and control groups mean, correlation and "t" test was used. (7)

3. RESULTS

The study was conducted to show the effect of whey Protein consumption on the selected physical fitness variables of Male sprinters. The statistical analysis of the data collected on twenty (N=20) male sprinters is presented. For each of the chosen variable, the results pertaining to significant difference, if any, between groups were assessed by "t" test and are presented in tables:

Table 1 shows that mean of standing broad jump of whey Protein consumption and control group was 2.683 and 2.071 respectively. The 't' value in case of standing broad jump of whey Protein consumption was 2.93. Since cal. t (=2.93) > tab t 0.05 (9) (=2.26), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

The mean of 50 Yard Dash of whey Protein consumption and control group was 6.27 and 6.66 respectively. The 't' value in case of standing broad jump of whey Protein consumption was 2.48. Since cal. t (=2.48) > tab t 0.05 (9) (=2.26), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

The mean of Pull Ups of whey Protein consumption and control group was 9.8 and 9.13 respectively. The 't' value in case of standing broad jump of whey Protein consumption was 2.44. Since cal. t (=2.44) > tab t 0.05 (9) (=2.26), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

The mean of Sit Ups of whey Protein consumption and control group was 39.26 and 40.26 respectively. The 't' value in case of standing broad jump of whey Protein consumption was 2.66. Since cal. t (=2.66) > tab t 0.05 (9) (=2.26), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Mean Value, Pearson Correlation and 't' Value of Physical Fitness of whey Protein Consumption and Control Group

Group	Variables	Number	Mean	Pearson Correlation	't' Value
Whey Protein	Standing Broad Jump	10	2.683	0.189	2.93
Control		10	2.071	0.526	0.70
Whey Protein	50 Yard Dash	10	6.276	0.124	2.48
Control		10	6.667	0.146	1.78
Whey Protein	Pull Ups	10	9.8	0.584	2.44
Control		10	9.13	0.250	1.76
Whey Protein	Sit Ups	10	39.26	0.102	2.66
Control		10	40.26	0.182	1.46
Whey Protein	Shuttle Run	10	9.668	0.124	3.14
Control		10	9.981	0.458	0.50
Whey Protein	12 Min. Run Walk	10	23.21	0.274	3.02
Control		10	24.19	0.332	0.53

The mean of Shuttle run of whey Protein consumption and control group was 9.66 and 9.98 respectively. The 't' value in case of standing broad jump of whey Protein consumption was 3.14. Since cal. $t (=3.14) > \text{tab } t_{0.05 (9)} (=2.26)$, H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

The mean of 12 Min. Run Walk of consumption of whey Protein and control group was 23.21 and 24.19 respectively. The 't' value in case of standing broad jump of whey Protein consumption was 3.02. Since cal. $t (=3.02) > \text{tab } t_{0.05 (9)} (=2.26)$, H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the physical fitness of whey Protein consumption showed significant improvement in standing broad jump, 50 yard dash; pull ups, sit ups, shuttle run and 12 minute run walk and insignificant result in control group. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence.

4. DISCUSSION

The result of present study shows the significant effect of whey Protein consumption on sprinters related to their Standing broad jump (Meters), 50 yard dash (Seconds), Pull-ups (Minutes), Sit-ups (Minutes), Shuttle run (Second), 12 min. run/walk. Whey Protein is traditionally used for general strengthening and recovery. Strengthen to the muscular Skelton system as well making this wonder full tonic. It is self-evident that the fit citizens are a nation's best assets and weak ones its liabilities. It is therefore the responsibility of every country to promote physical fitness of its citizens because physical fitness is the basic requirement for most of the tasks to be undertaken by an individual in his daily life. So present study show whey Protein consumption increase the strength and coordinate ability so there is no side effect recommended by the doctors and ashwagandha help to increase the strength and coordinative ability of the players and use for other games which requires more explosive strength, abdominal strength and coordinative ability.

In conclusion; keeping the results and discussion in view the conclusions drawn shows the significant effect of whey Protein consumption on sprinters related to their Standing broad jump (Meters), 50 yard dash (Seconds), Pull-ups (Minutes), Sit-ups (Minutes), Shuttle run (Second), 12 min. run/walk. With reference to the physical fitness between whey Protein consumption (experimental) and control, significant difference is noted in all diameters including standing broad jump, 50 yard dash, Pull-ups, Sit-ups, Shuttle run, 12 min. run/walk.

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